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Indications for Preterm Cesarean Section and Fetomaternal Outcomes

Marina Khan^{1,*} · Raheel Sikandar² · Madiha Abbasi³ · Aqsa⁴ · Saba Ashraf⁵ · Batool Meer⁶¹⁻⁶ Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad

* Corresponding Author: Dr. Marina Khan, MBBS, MS (OBGYN), Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad.

Email: marinaKhan181@gmail.com

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE

To identify the indications for performing preterm cesarean sections (CS), and to assess the fetomaternal outcomes in patients undergoing preterm CS at Liaquat University Medical Hospital, Hyderabad.

METHODS

The study employed a descriptive cross-sectional approach. In total, 172 pregnant women, whose ages ranged between 20 and 40 years, underwent a preterm CS before reaching 37 completed weeks of gestation. Using a non-probability consecutive sampling strategy, participants were selected for inclusion into this study. Maternal and fetal outcomes were evaluated until the seventh day post-delivery.

RESULTS

The mean maternal age was 32.03 ± 7.96 years. Hypertensive disorders (n=57; 33.1%) represented the most frequent indication for a preterm C-section. Other indications included previous cesarean section (20.35%), oligohydramnios (15.12%), malpresentation with preterm labour (14.53%), antepartum haemorrhage (10.46%), and preterm rupture of membranes (6.4%). Of the mothers studied, 78.5% had positive maternal outcomes, whereas 21.5% had negative maternal outcomes, primarily due to postpartum hemorrhage (62.2%). There was no statistical correlation between an individual adverse maternal complication and gestational age ($\chi^2 = 5.29$, $P = 0.259$). An estimated 85.14% of newborns survived after birth. Neonatal and fetal mortality accounted for approximately 14.86% of births. 65.4% of neonates who died had been admitted to the NICU with respiratory distress syndrome. There was a very strong association between the gestational age at delivery and the risk of fetal mortality ($\chi^2 = 50.38$, $p < 0.001$).

CONCLUSION

In general, preterm C-sections tend to be associated with positive maternal and perinatal outcomes, and hypertensive disorders are the most common indication for performing a preterm C-section. However, there is a considerable decrease in the safety of both mother and fetus when premature birth occurs prior to 28 completed weeks of gestation, which has been demonstrated to correlate with a high rate of fetal death. These findings highlight the necessity of complete prenatal care and the prompt treatment of maternal medical conditions that may develop during pregnancy.

Introduction

Preterm birth is the birth of a baby before 37 weeks of gestation and is a major public health problem due to its numerous short and long term negative effects on the quality of life [1]. Although the risk of mortality and morbidity are greatest during the earliest stages of pregnancy, late preterm infants have increased risks of various negative outcomes when compared to full-term babies [2].

Over 10% of all pregnancies will end in a preterm birth [3] and developing countries suffer disproportionately high burdens; for example, Pakistan has one of the highest rates of preterm birth in the world, approximately 16 per 100 live births [4]. Simultaneously, the rates of cesarean section (CS) have been rising progressively and unusually worldwide. In Pakistan, the rate of cesarean deliveries rose from 3.2% in 1990 to 19.6% in 2018 [5].

The combination of preterm birth and CS present unique clinical challenges. Biomechanically and biochemically, CS bypasses the biochemical and biomechanical mechanisms of vaginal labor which enhance fetal lung maturation, thereby increasing the risk of respiratory disease in the newborn [6]. For mothers, performing a CS in a preterm pregnancy creates particular surgical difficulties. The lower uterine segment is usually underdeveloped and as such most require a vertical incision through the upper uterine segment [6, 7]. This type of surgery increases the risk of both maternal morbidity (e.g., increased intraoperative bleeding), and severe maternal complication (i.e., increased risk of uterine rupture in future pregnancies) [6, 7].

Emergency CS are also associated with an elevated risk of poor neonatal outcomes [8]. Planned preterm CS may protect against fetal demise and birth injury but it also places the fetus and the premature neonate at great risk of serious morbidity [9]. A comprehensive review of the available research demonstrates a marked paucity of research regarding specific-maternal outcomes for preterm CS in developing countries [10, 11]. This study aims to identify the medical indications for preterm CS and systematically assess the resulting fetomaternal outcomes at a tertiary care center.

Subjects, Materials & Methods

STUDY DESIGN AND LOCATION

This was a descriptive cross sectional study that was done in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Liaquat University Hospital in Hyderabad, Pakistan. The study was completed over a 6 month time frame from July 2022 to December 2022. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad prior to commencement of the study.

SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING METHOD

The sample size of 172 participants was calculated using Raosoft® software based on an assumed 20% prevalence of preterm cesarean section, with a 90% confidence level and 5% margin of error. We recruited participants into our study by using a non probability consecutive sampling method.

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

We included all pregnant women who met the following criteria:

- Pregnant women between the ages of 20 to 40 years old.
- Underwent a premature CS at a gestational age of less than 37 weeks.

We excluded women from the study based on the following criteria:

- Women who refused to participate.
- Confirmed diagnosis of diabetes.
- Fetus with a known birth defect.

PROCEDURE FOR COLLECTING DATA

Each participant provided written informed consent after being informed about the study. Maternal medical history and baseline clinical data were recorded for all participants. The indications for cesarean section were documented, and fetomaternal outcomes were assessed up to the seventh day postpartum. All data were recorded using a predesigned data collection form.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

We entered the quantitative data into the SPSS version 20.0 and then analyzed it. We presented the quantitative data as mean \pm SD. We presented categorical variables as simple frequencies and percentages. We stratified the data according to effect modifiers related to the outcome measures. We used the Chi-squared test to determine whether there were statistically significant associations, with p values \leq 0.05 indicating statistically significant differences.

Results

DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL FEATURES

A total of 172 women undergoing preterm CS were included in the study. The mean maternal age was 32.03 \pm 7.96 years. Most participants were between 28–34 years of age and a majority were unbooked for antenatal care. Most patients were from urban areas and belonged to a low socioeconomic background. Detailed demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants (N=172)

Parameter	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (Years)		
20–27	14	8.14%
28–34	111	64.53%
35–40	47	27.33%
Catchment Area		
Urban	112	65.11%
Rural	60	34.89%
Booking Status		
Booked	66	38.38%
Unbooked	106	61.62%
Socioeconomic Status		
Middle Class	35	20.35%
Poor	137	79.65%
Maternal BMI		
Underweight (<18.5)	67	38.9%
Healthy (18.5 – 24.9)	58	33.8%
Overweight (25.0 – 29.9)	35	20.4%
Obese (>30.0)	12	6.9%

INDICATIONS AND MATERNAL OUTCOMES

The three most common indications for preterm CS were hypertensive disorders, previous cesarean section, and oligohydramnios.

Table 2: Indications for Pre-term CS (N=172)

Indication	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Hypertensive disorders	57	33.14%
Previous C-Section	35	20.35%
Oligohydramnios	26	15.12%
Malpresentation with Preterm labour	25	14.53%
Antepartum Haemorrhage	18	10.46%
Preterm Rupture of Membranes	11	6.4%

Overall, 78.5% (n = 135) of women who underwent preterm CS experienced favourable maternal outcomes, while 21.5% (n = 37) developed adverse maternal outcomes. Postpartum hemorrhage was the most common complication, followed by ICU admission and maternal death. The distribution of adverse maternal outcomes according to gestational age is presented in Table 3. No statistically significant association was observed between the type of maternal complication and gestational age ($\chi^2 = 5.29$, $p = 0.259$).

Table 3: Distribution of Poor Maternal Outcomes by Gestational Age (N=37)

Poor Maternal Outcome	< 28 weeks	28 to 32 weeks	32 to 37 Weeks	Total (n, %)
Postpartum Hemorrhage	5 (21.7%)	12 (52.2%)	6 (26.1%)	23 (62.2%)
ICU Admission	6 (54.5%)	3 (27.3%)	2 (18.2%)	11 (29.7%)
Maternal Death	2 (66.7%)	1 (33.3%)	0	3 (8.1%)

$\chi^2 = 5.29$, $p = 0.259$

FETAL OUTCOMES

A total of 175 neonates were delivered from 172 pregnancies, including three twin pregnancies. Overall neonatal survival was 85.14% (n = 149), while 14.86% (n = 26) resulted in perinatal death. Seventeen neonates (10%) required admission to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), most commonly due to respiratory distress syndrome. The distribution of fetal outcomes according to gestational age is shown in Table 4. A statistically significant association was observed between gestational age at delivery and fetal mortality ($\chi^2 = 50.38$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 4: Fetal Outcomes and Characteristics by Gestational Age (N=175)

Fetal Characteristics	Extremely Preterm (< 28 weeks)	Very Preterm (28 – 32 weeks)	Moderate/Late Preterm (32 – 37 weeks)
Number of Babies (%)	14 (8%)	67 (38.3%)	94 (53.7%)
Mean Birth Weight (kg)	1.7 ± 1.55	1.85 ± 0.87	2.77 ± 1.21
Alive	1 (7.14%)	55 (82.1%)	93 (98.9%)
Still Born	6 (42.86%)	3 (4.47%)	0
Neonatal Death	7 (50%)	9 (13.43%)	1 (1.1%)

$\chi^2 = 50.38$, $p < 0.001$ (Alive vs. Dead outcomes)

Discussion

The study's demographic characteristics show that a large percentage of women who had a premature CS were between the ages of 28-34 years (64.53%), did not have booked antenatal care (61.62%), were residents of an urban area (65.11%), and came from a low socioeconomic status (79.65%). These demographic results are

generally consistent with other studies in similar populations; Richa et al. stated that a similar trend occurred in their study, which indicated that there was an overrepresentation of unbooked patients from lower socioeconomic backgrounds between the ages of 20-30 years [12].

The common medical reasons for premature surgical delivery included hypertensive disorders (including pre-eclampsia and eclampsia) as the major reason at 33.14%, followed by a previous history of a CS (20.35%), and oligohydramnios (15.12%). The findings of this study differ from several international cohorts. For example, Lydon-Rochelle et al. reported that the most common indication for a CS was failure to progress (60.1%), and that fetal indications accounted for only 5.8% of the indications [13].

In addition, Peaceman et al. and Ezechi et al. identified cephalopelvic disproportion (CPD) and failed trial of labor as the most common indications for a CS in their respective studies at 44.9% and 52.6% [14, 15]. Within the regional context, Richa et al. found CPD (23%) and scar tenderness (15.76%) to be more common indications for a CS than hypertensive disorders [12]. It is probable that the high frequency of hypertensive disorders resulting in premature surgical intervention in our population relates to the high number of unbooked pregnancies with inadequate routine antenatal monitoring.

Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) was the most serious maternal complication of the study and affected 62.2% of the subset of women who experienced poor outcomes. This is greater than the PPH rate of 48.55% reported in a study by Goel et al. [18]. Furthermore, 29.7% of the women experiencing poor outcomes in our study required ICU admission. This is different than the findings of Bhowmik et al., in which fewer women were admitted to the ICU, and surgical difficulties such as severe adhesions and difficulty opening the abdomen (41.11%) were the most common complications [17]. Surgical adhesions are a known risk factor for women with a history of prior CS, as confirmed by Lyell et al. [16].

The outcomes of the fetus after a preterm CS are a concern. While the overall neonatal survival rate of our study was very good (85.14%), we observed a high level of requirement for NICU admission (10% of all babies, and 65.4% of those who ultimately died due to respiratory distress syndrome). The total fetal and neonatal mortality of our cohort was 14.86%. This is in line with Anagha et al., who concluded that the perinatal morbidity is much higher for preterm CSs compared to term deliveries [19]. However, Ismail et al. reported a better outcome in their cohort, with a 4.9% fresh stillbirth rate and a 1.5% early neonatal death rate, although NICU admissions were higher in their cohort at 29.4% [20]. We conclude from our data that fetal mortality is highly related to the gestational age of delivery indicating that extreme prematurity increases neonatal mortality risk.

There are two potential limitations to this study. First, the sample size was smaller (N=172) than many studies in the field, potentially limiting the generalizability of the results to larger populations. Second, because this research was performed in a public sector tertiary care hospital, the clinical decisions made by physicians were sometimes driven by patient preferences; a few patient preference occasionally influenced the decision for cesarean delivery without a full trial of labor.

Conclusion

Preterm cesarean section was associated with acceptable maternal and neonatal outcomes in most cases. The most common reason for preterm surgical intervention in our study setting has been hypertensive disorders; however, both extreme prematurity and the presence of significant maternal comorbidity can severely compromise the safety of a CS. In order to minimize the risk of postpartum hemorrhage and neonatal mortality among extremely

premature infants, an improved focus must be made on increasing engagement in ANC. The early identification and active management of comorbid conditions, specifically PIH, prior to emergency surgical intervention will provide optimal outcomes for both mother and infant.

Author Contributions

In accordance with the ICMJE guidelines, all authors have made substantial contributions to the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Author	Conception & Design	Data Collection & Analysis	Drafting & Revision	Final Approval
Marina Khan (MK)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Raheel Sikandar (RS)	✓	—	✓	✓
Madiha Abbasi (MA)	—	✓	✓	✓
Aqsa (A)	—	✓	—	✓
Saba Ashraf (SA)	—	✓	—	✓
Batool Meer (BM)	—	✓	✓	✓

DECLARATIONS

Ethical Approval: The study was approved by the Ethical Review Committee of Liaquat University Hospital (ERC Letter No: LUMHS/REC/-72).

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